

Vision of sustainable trade regimes

MATS Deliverable 5.1

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Summary

WP5 started in M21 (March 2023), according to the work plan schedule in the Description of Action in the GA. WP5 builds on results of WP1-4 and WP6. The aim of the WP is to jointly develop a MATS vision of a more sustainable, resilient food system that builds on equitable economic partnerships in agricultural trade as well as transition pathways towards this vision, which will be described in deliverable 5.2.

The visioning process focuses on a joint vision of the whole MATS consortium within the context of alternative trade regimes. The subsequent webinars provide the foundation for the development of the transition pathways. The following activities were conducted for this purpose:

(1) Mini-Workshop in the context of the MATS project meeting on May 15-16, 2023 was organized with background information on the visioning process and first ideas on the vision elements based on different case studies.

(2) Exchange with case study representatives took place to collect further ideas on vision elements.

(3) This assisted in identifying shared vision statements in the co-creation workshop held during MATS project meeting in October 23-27, 2023 in Moshi/Tanzania. This workshop was the core of the visioning process. In addition to the vision statements already first input for concrete actions leading to the accomplishment of the vision were collected there.

(4) With this background four webinars on February 5-8, 2024 were organized in preparation of the workshop on transition pathways in March 5-8, 2024 in Brussels. In this online meetings additional actions were collected and discussed taking into account the input from the workshop in Moshi/Tanzania.

The visioning process is summarized in a policy brief, which is as well part of deliverable 5.1. As it gives a good overview of the visioning process it will be presented in the forefront of this deliverable.

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Table of Contents

Summary	2
Table of Contents	4
Policy brief: The MATS Vision – Visioning process on desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments.....	6
Introduction	6
Highlights	6
Discussion points/Policy suggestions	7
1. Mini-Workshop in the context of the MATS project meeting in May 2023..	9
Background.....	9
Approach	9
2. Exchange with case study representatives	10
Background.....	10
Approach	10
3. Visioning Workshop for Transition Pathways.....	11
Background.....	11
Approach	11
Results	12
Sustainability dimension - Economy and Markets	12
Sustainability dimension - Social and Human.....	14
Sustainability dimension - Natural Capital	15
Sustainability dimension - Policy, Governance and Regulation.....	17
4. Developing Transition Pathways - The Webinar Series	19
Background.....	19
Approach and tools	19
Results	20
Sustainability dimension - Economy and Markets	21
Sustainability dimension - Social and Human.....	24

Sustainability dimension - Natural Capital	25
Sustainability dimension - Policy, Governance and Regulation.....	29
Follow-up	32

Policy brief: The MATS Vision – Visioning process on desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments

Introduction

To meet the overall goal of deriving transition pathways for desirable changes in agricultural trade relations towards greater sustainability and to formulate corresponding policy recommendations, it is necessary to define where we as a group aim to go. The MATS visioning assists to define this direction and describes desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments with a focus on equitable economic partnerships in sustainable agricultural trade for the time horizon 2035+.

In broad terms, we want to work towards a more sustainable and resilient food system with economic and trade partnerships where partners recognize each other as “equals” (Juncker, 2018). To find transition pathways towards this desired state, this definition had to be deconstructed into more concrete vision statements with the help of the 15 MATS case studies contributing their on-the-ground/evidence-based insights.

Highlights

The visioning process is a participatory approach including stakeholders directly involved in the MATS consortium. These stakeholders will continue to play a pivotal role in developing transition pathways. Additional stakeholders and external experts from industry, research, policy as well as civil society will be invited to join the discussion and expand the knowledge base.

The visioning process was initiated by reviewing the 15 MATS case studies’ mid-term reports. Vision statements were derived and collected along the four previously defined sustainability dimensions – “policy, governance and regulation”; “social and human dimensions”; “natural capital”, and “economy and markets”. In addition, online consultations with the different case studies were held to get preliminary information on the collected statements. With this foundation, the MATS case studies and core team members - especially those engaged with institutional, regulatory and legal frameworks and with

civil-society actors, stakeholders and policymakers - came together in Moshi/Tanzania to discuss the findings in a moderated participatory workshop setting. This approach ensured that relevant issues were considered and discussed. The results of this process were again reflected in a series of webinars, open to the MATS case studies, core team as well as external participants from industry, research or civil society.

FIGURE 5: OVERVIEW OF THE STEPS OF THE VISIONING PROCESS

During the visioning workshop the inner circle of stakeholders discussed a desired future state of sustainable agricultural trade in 2035+. It became apparent that despite their differences, the case studies have many areas of overlap in their common objectives for sustainable agricultural trade.

During the visioning workshop, the development of transition pathways for more sustainable agricultural trade was also started by collecting initial ideas for action aimed at realizing the desired vision. These will help to derive policy recommendations as the project evolves.

Discussion points/Policy suggestions

The case study reports and individual discussions with the case studies **provided a differentiated picture of a desired future**. Among the vision statements considered and discussed included the following: (a) "All workers

on cocoa farms earn at least a living wage”, which is regarded as closely aligned to a regional context in nature and can be applied to several country contexts; (b) “Alignment of EU agricultural, trade, investment, and development policies for sustainable value chains”, which is considered holistic in nature but can also be transferable to different regions; (c) “strong local institutions and capacities for sustainable trade” whose actions were already brought to the discussion in the visioning workshop”; and, (d) “established bodies provide some capacity building initiatives to processors and exporters for meeting WTO rules, regulations, and EU requirements”, where several actions were added during the four online sessions, covering the whole time range from short, middle to long term.

It noteworthy that since agricultural trade is interwoven in the agri-food system and constitutes only one step in the value chain, **a considerable part of the vision statements addressed the state of agricultural production.**

The visioning process on desirable changes in trade regimes, trade relations and instruments revealed, among others, that old and new policies are needed, that sustainable water management practices in agriculture touches all four dimensions of sustainability, and that decentralization and less bureaucracy may be critical factors in guaranteeing smallholder farmers access to markets and fair prices.

1. Mini-Workshop in the context of the MATS project meeting in May 2023

Background

In order to initiate the visioning process within the MATS consortium, the MATS project meeting in May 15-16, 2023 was used to communicate the approach within the consortium and give information on the further proceeding.

Approach

At first background information on visioning was given. It was highlighted that a vision should describe a desirable future, which substantially differs from the status quo. A shared vision is highly relevant for initiating transition processes and it should be created using a bottom-up approach to involve all relevant stakeholders. Furthermore, the difference of visioning and scenario building was explained.

The following questions, leading the visioning process, were presented:

- What is important in the area of trade? Which aspects must be taken into account?
- What are the overlaps among the SDGs?
- What is important to MATS?
- Are there any particularly relevant areas in each Case Study?

To close with, it was announced that in the forefront of the visioning workshop in Moshi/Tanzania the question 'What areas should be covered by the statements in the vision' will be addressed in close coordination with the Case Studies.

2. Exchange with case study representatives

Background

In preparation of the visioning workshop in Moshi/Tanzania the Case Studies were already involved in a participatory process.

Approach

The process of collecting the vision statements for the Case Studies involved a step-by-step synthesis aimed at transitioning from individual visions at the Case Study level to a shared vision for the whole group (MATS). Initially, efforts were focused on understanding the individual visions of each Case Study. To achieve this, the Case Studies were requested to articulate their own vision statements and outline challenges using provided templates.

Drawing upon information gathered from previous work packages, particularly mid-term reports, some statements for the individual case studies had already been identified. These statements were then incorporated into the table. Adjustments were welcomed, allowing for the adaptation or removal of statements as necessary. For each sustainability dimension, between several statements were formulated, envisioning desired positive developments and highlighting the most significant characteristics or features expected by the year 2035 and beyond.

In addition to outlining positive developments, the main challenges faced by each Case Study were also described, providing a comprehensive understanding of both the envisioned future and the obstacles to be overcome.

Then the team of Fraunhofer ISI screened the input for shared elements among the Case Studies. It was identified which core statements could be used to address several Case Studies at once. In more detail, concrete expressions were searched for, which should definitely be discussed by the MATS consortium in the visioning workshop.

3. Visioning Workshop for Transition Pathways

Background

The goal of the visioning workshop was to facilitate collaborative envisioning of successful management and adaptation to upcoming changes across various dimensions such as environmental, social sustainability, market and investment, trade policy, and government. The workshop aimed at the formulation of vision statements that are shared by all case studies within the MATS project as well as develop initial ideas for implementable option for action (transition pathways).

Approach

The workshop took place in Moshi, Tanzania on October 24th and 25th, 2023. The workshop was conducted in the context of the MATS Annual Meeting, with the concept and facilitation provided by Fraunhofer ISI. The target group included MATS Case Studies Representatives, external workshop participants, and further project partners.

On the first day of the workshop, participants were welcomed and introduced to the visioning and workshop approach. The agenda and the background of the workshop were presented, and participants were given an opportunity to introduce themselves. The first work step involved dividing the case study related people into their most interested dimensions of sustainability and dividing the rest of the group equally into the four dimensions of sustainability.

During the working phase, participants prioritized and expanded vision statement written on cards and identified potentials and challenges for implementation of the vision. The vision statements were identified in advance in coordination with the case studies (see chapter 2 of this deliverable). Conflicts were identified and resolved if necessary. The work continued in new group constellations using the World Cafe-Approach. In the plenary session, hosts presented short summaries of the discussed topics per dimension, and all participants voted on the most important points for a MATS vision (see

results section below). There were four hosts supporting the discussions at the tables from the following partners: ESRF, UPM, OWW, NWU.

On the second day, the workshop started with a summary of the results from the previous day and an introduction to the workshop approach for day two. Group formations were done, and participants worked on templates on actions to reach the defined vision statements defined the day before. Numbered templates were processed, and clustered on the wall around the vision statements. The workshop concluded with a personal review, final roundtable, and wrap-up session where participants discussed the greatest potentials and challenges on the way to a common vision.

The workshop ended with an outlook on the next steps. The collected ideas and outcomes from the workshop will contribute to the development of transition pathways and policy recommendations for sustainable trade relations in agricultural value chains as part of the MATS project.

Results

In the following the vision statements per sustainability dimension are listed, which were developed during the first day of the visioning workshop.

Sustainability dimension - Economy and Markets

Ensuring Market Access and Fair Prices for Smallholder Farmers: We aim to create a fair and accessible marketplace for smallholder farmers, where they receive equitable prices for their produce. By fostering transparent trading practices and reducing intermediaries, we want to build a market environment that promotes sustainability and rewards hard work.

Protecting Living Wage Income for Small-Scale Producers: We envision an agricultural sector where small-scale producers earn a living wage that ensures a decent standard of living. This encompasses fair labour practices, equitable compensation, and improved social safety nets for the most vulnerable workers in the food chain.

Guaranteeing Fair Prices for Collectors and Processors: We strive for a value chain where collectors and processors are paid fairly for their services, acknowledging their vital role in bringing products from the farm to the

market. This seeks to eliminate exploitation and ensure equitable distribution of value across the entire agricultural sector.

Holding Companies Accountable for Farm Gate Prices: We aspire to create a business environment where companies take full responsibility for farm gate prices, ensuring they are fair and transparent. This promotes accountability and discourages outsourcing to traders who exploit smallholder farmers.

Promoting Local, Fair, and Sustainable Production and Trade: We aspire a thriving local economy supported by fair and sustainable production and trade practices. We aim to foster resilient local food systems that prioritize local sourcing and build strong territorial markets that encourage regional collaboration.

Enhancing Value Addition and Competitiveness in the Sector: We envision an agricultural sector with enhanced value addition, leading to increased competitiveness and new market opportunities. This includes investment in local production and processing, allowing small-scale producers to capture more value from their products.

Strengthening Regional and Local Food Systems for Greater Resilience: We attempt to strike a balance between resilient local/national value chains and robust intra-regional trade. By strengthening regional markets, such as the EAC, SADC, and ECOWAS economic blocs, we aim to create immediate markets for value-added products and pave the way for global expansion.

Improving Transparency in Price Setting for Coffee and Other Crops: We desire a market where price setting is transparent, involving farmers at the cooperative level and ensuring fairness in transactions. By promoting clear and open pricing mechanisms, we aim to build trust and confidence among all stakeholders in the value chain.

Investing in Local Production and Processing for a Stronger Economy: We aspire to build a robust economy by investing in local production and processing facilities. This vision encourages the development of local businesses, creating job opportunities and fostering a sustainable and resilient agricultural sector.

Reforming Futures Markets to Include Farmer Interests and Promote Transparency: We wish for a reformed futures market where transparency, accountability, and respect for human rights and the environment are paramount. By incorporating farmer interests and fostering collaboration, we aim to create a futures market that serves the common good and supports sustainable agricultural practices.

Sustainability dimension - Social and Human

Empowering Rural Communities through Social Protection and Self-Help Initiatives: We envision a future where rural communities flourish through robust social protection programs, small grants, and self-help initiatives. By encouraging community work, cooperative associations, and crop/livestock insurance, we aim to foster a culture of resilience and shared prosperity.

Promoting Black Economic Empowerment in Agriculture: We strive for a transformative agricultural sector where land ownership and opportunities are equitably distributed, addressing the historical inequalities of past policies. This transformation will be driven by initiatives that support and empower black farmers and ensure equitable access to resources.

Supporting Small-Scale Producers and Empowering Marginalized Communities: We aspire to create a thriving ecosystem that supports small-scale producers and marginalized communities. This includes providing resources, training, and market access to ensure that every producer has the opportunity to succeed and contribute to sustainable food systems.

Championing Consumer Awareness and Ethical Production: We opt for a marketplace where consumers actively seek and demand ethically produced products. By promoting consumer education and transparency, we aim to build a value chain that is both socially responsible and environmentally sustainable.

Ensuring Fair Wages and Decent Working Conditions for Agricultural Workers: We envision an agricultural sector where all workers receive fair wages, safe working conditions, and the benefits they deserve. This includes eradicating child labour and reducing gender disparities to create an inclusive and equitable workforce.

Promoting Gender Equality and Asset Ownership for Women and Youth: We aim for a society where gender equality is achieved in asset ownership, allowing women and youth to fully participate in agricultural production and land ownership. By challenging discriminatory cultural norms, we aim to ensure that everyone has equal rights to property and resources.

Improving Collaboration for Sustainable Value Chains: We strive for a future where producers, retailers, and consumers work together to create sustainable value chains. This emphasizes traceability, transparency, and fair value distribution to ensure a more ethical and efficient food system.

Guaranteeing Food Security and the Right to Nutritious Food: We pursue a world where food security and the right to nutritious food are guaranteed for all. We aim to achieve this by supporting smallholder farmers, promoting food sovereignty, and addressing the root causes of food insecurity.

Strengthening Co-operatives to Enhance Market Participation and Reduce Rural Poverty: We attempt to build a future where co-operatives play a central role in enhancing market participation for smallholder farmers, leading to increased incomes and reduced rural poverty. By fostering a sense of community and shared goals, co-operatives will be instrumental in achieving sustainable rural development.

Sustainability dimension - Natural Capital

Integrating Sustainable Farming Practices into the Agricultural Value Chain: We envision an agricultural value chain that integrates sustainable farming practices, addressing the impacts of changing dietary habits, climate change, and environmental justice. This promotes transparency, with processors and retailers providing clear information on sustainable practices and encouraging further product labelling to meet evolving consumer expectations.

Ensuring Efficient Use of Water Resources in Water-Scarce Regions: We opt for a resilient agricultural sector that prioritizes efficient water use, especially in water-scarce regions. By fostering innovative practices, global financial support, and collaboration, we aim to achieve sustainable water management, promoting both environmental and economic resilience.

Conducting Environmental Impact Assessments for Trade: We aspire a world where environmental impact assessments are a standard practice for all trade activities. This seeks to ensure that international trade complies with environmental regulations and promotes sustainability, with a focus on reducing the ecological footprint of agricultural products.

Ensuring Compliance with Environmental Regulations: We opt for an agricultural sector where all stakeholders comply with environmental regulations, ensuring that production practices align with global sustainability goals. This promotes accountability, with governments and other actors enforcing standards that protect the environment.

Aligning Global Sustainability Standards with Local Realities: We aim to create a framework where global sustainability standards are compatible with local realities. This emphasizes institutional fit, ensuring that these standards support local communities while advancing global sustainability objectives.

Promoting Animal Welfare and Environmental Sustainability in Production Regulations: We opt for a set of production regulations and standards that prioritize animal welfare and environmental sustainability. By incorporating humane treatment of animals and sustainable practices, we aim to create a more ethical and environmentally conscious agricultural sector.

Addressing Environmental Risks through Business Model Changes and Sourcing Practices: We envision companies that proactively change their business models and sourcing practices to address root causes of environmental risks. This includes implementing Human Rights and Environmental Due Diligence (HREDD), with a focus on mitigating, monitoring, and reporting negative impacts in the value chain, especially regarding greenhouse gas emissions.

Improving Productivity with Best Agronomic Practices and Genetic Innovations: We aim to improve agricultural productivity by promoting best agronomic practices and innovative genetic materials. This seeks to enhance yield while minimizing environmental impact, contributing to a more sustainable and productive agricultural sector.

Promoting Climate and Environmental Justice in Agricultural Practices: We aspire an agricultural sector that champions climate and environmental justice, addressing the disproportionate impact of climate change on vulnerable communities. This promotes practices that mitigate climate risks and support those most affected by environmental changes.

Leveraging Global Financial Instruments for Sustainable Development and Economic Resilience: We strive for a world where global financial instruments are harnessed to support cooperation in sustainable development and economic resilience. By providing the necessary resources and support, we aim to create an environment conducive to sustainable agricultural practices and robust value chains.

Sustainability dimension - Policy, Governance and Regulation

Developing Strong, Equitable, and Sensible Policies for Local Value Chains: We envision a future where ECOWAS and national West African (WA) governments implement robust policies that support investment in local value chains and ensure market protection. This promotes a balanced approach that fosters local economic growth, food security, and equitable opportunities for all stakeholders.

Providing Comprehensive Capacity Building for Processors and Exporters: We want to create established bodies that offer extensive capacity-building initiatives for processors and exporters, enabling them to meet World Trade Organization (WTO) rules, European Union (EU) requirements, and other global standards. This includes support for certification, technology adoption, and value addition, empowering businesses to thrive in a global market.

Promoting Transparency in Environmental Sustainability Practices and Standards: We aspire to increase transparency in environmental sustainability practices, ensuring that production methods and standards are clearly specified in agreements. This addresses the need for dedicated sustainability units within processors and retailers, emphasizing their role in sustainability reporting and aligning with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI).

Providing Free Public Research and Extension Services for Key Agricultural Products: Our aim is a public system where research and extension services for the husbandry of key agricultural products like cassava,

banana, goats, and cocoa are freely available to farmers. This supports the dissemination of knowledge and best practices, fostering agricultural innovation and sustainability.

Regulating Markets with a Focus on Food Security: We envision market regulations that prioritize food security, ensuring that agricultural policies are designed to meet the needs of local populations while promoting sustainable production. This seeks to create a stable environment that supports local farmers and secures access to nutritious food for all.

Advancing the Representation and Fair Treatment of Sustainable Agricultural Products: We want to create a world where sustainable agricultural products receive fair treatment and representation in global markets. By promoting equitable policies and reducing barriers, we aim to encourage the production and trade of environmentally responsible goods.

Establishing Robust Enforcement Systems for Agricultural Obligations: We aim to create an enforcement system that holds all stakeholders accountable for their agricultural obligations. This includes mechanisms to ensure compliance with environmental, human, labour, and animal rights standards, fostering a culture of responsibility and accountability.

Empowering Farmers as Key Actors for Change: We aspire a society where farmers are recognized and empowered as key actors for change in the agricultural sector. By providing them with the resources, knowledge, and support they need, we aim to enable farmers to drive innovation and sustainability within their communities.

Promoting Fundamental Rights in Agricultural Practices: We envision an agricultural sector that upholds fundamental human, environmental, labour, and animal rights. This encourages fair treatment, ethical practices, and a commitment to sustainability at every level of the value chain.

4. Developing Transition Pathways - The Webinar Series

Background

The "Developing Transition Pathways - The Webinar Series" was organized to prepare for a workshop on transition pathways and policy recommendations in Brussels in March. The series consisted of four webinars, each focusing on one dimension of sustainability. The goal was to gather input and perspectives from a wide range of stakeholders, including experts from case studies, trade, and agriculture.

The invitation sent to case study representatives emphasized the importance of their involvement in sharing the invitation with their respective stakeholders. The webinars aimed to integrate "the view from outside" the MATS project, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives.

Approach and tools

Each webinar followed a consistent agenda. It began with a dial-in and technical check to ensure smooth participation. The session then commenced with a warm welcome and introduction, setting the stage for the discussions that followed.

The presentation of the Miro board and workshop approach was a crucial part of each webinar. The Miro board served as a collaborative platform, allowing participants to visualize and contribute to the development of transition pathways. The agenda encouraged participants to generate new actions, provide suggestions, and engage in discussions to improve and adapt existing approaches.

Following the active participation and contribution phase, time was allocated for reflection. Participants had the opportunity to absorb the discussions, review the actions collected, and draw connections between different ideas and perspectives.

Next steps in the project were discussed at the end of each webinar, providing updates on the progress made and outlining the future direction. The webinars

concluded with a formal end-of-event message, expressing gratitude to the participants for their valuable contributions.

Throughout the webinars, the Teams platform facilitated seamless online collaboration, while the Miro board served as a visual aid and interactive workspace for participants to collectively begin to shape the transition pathways.

Results

During the webinars, participants actively shared their ideas and suggestions on the measures that could be taken to achieve the shared vision. To organize and categorize these ideas, a timeline approach was adopted. The participants' ideas were divided into three categories: short-term measures (up to 3 years), medium-term measures (3 to 7 years), and long-term measures (7 to 10 years).

The resulting roadmap was structured based on the thematic elements of the vision. The thematic elements served as the foundation for organizing and prioritizing the measures identified by the participants. By aligning the roadmap with the vision's themes, it ensured that the proposed measures were coherent and contributed to the overall objectives.

The timeline categorization provided a clear sense of the urgency and timeframes associated with each measure. Short-term measures aimed at addressing immediate actions within a relatively short period, while medium-term measures focused on more comprehensive initiatives that could be implemented within a few years. Long-term measures were designed to tackle complex challenges and required a more extended timeframe for implementation.

Below, actions collected for each of the four dimensions of sustainability will be presented. Each action, in addition to its title, was allocated in time to short term, middle term, or long term. Furthermore, a brief description accompanies

each action. Additionally, alongside the actions gathered in the webinars, those from the workshop in Tanzania³ will also be listed.

Sustainability dimension - Economy and Markets

Voluntary or regulated disclosure of including living wage in business objectives (short-term & middle-term): Implement a mandatory requirement for companies to include the cost of a living wage in their product prices to ensure fair compensation for workers. Establish a standardized reporting framework for companies to publicly disclose the wages of their workers, enabling consumers to make informed purchasing decisions.

Sustainable investment in agri-food sector (short-term): Facilitate partnerships between foreign private-sector investors and agri-food actors in developing countries to provide the necessary financial resources for sustainable development aligned with the SDGs. Create investment funds specifically targeted at supporting sustainable practices in the agri-food sector.

Sustainable Investment (short-term): Encourage investments in value-adding activities closer to the farm gates, such as processing and packaging, to increase the value of agricultural products and reduce dependency on external markets. Develop transparent and accountable investment guidelines and criteria that prioritize environmental, social, and governance factors.

Promote producers associations or cooperatives (middle-term):

Provide training programs and resources to support smallholders in forming and strengthening producers associations or cooperatives, enabling them to overcome administrative hurdles and increase competitiveness. Streamline administrative processes and reduce paperwork for smallholders to make it easier for them to participate in cooperatives.

Decrease bureaucracy to democratize production (middle-term): Conduct a comprehensive review of existing bureaucratic processes and

³ In the second part of the workshop, first ideas for actions to reach the defined vision statements were collected.

regulations in the agricultural sector to identify areas for simplification and streamlining.

Support decentralization and competition within importing markets

(middle-term): Develop policies and initiatives that promote competition and diversification of suppliers within importing markets, reducing the dominance of centralized markets. Provide support and resources to local businesses and producers to enhance their competitiveness and expand market access.

Food and nutrition security in developing countries

(middle-term & long-term): Integrate food and nutrition security into national development plans and policies, with a focus on ensuring availability, access, and stability of food, as well as addressing malnutrition and dietary deficiencies. Invest in agricultural research and development, infrastructure, and social protection programs to improve food and nutrition security in developing countries.

"Naming, blaming, shaming"

(middle-term): Establish a public platform or database that publicly identifies and exposes companies engaged in unethical practices in their supply chains, encouraging them to improve their practices. Collaborate with civil society organizations and consumer advocacy groups to raise awareness and promote consumer boycotts of companies involved in unethical practices.

Reverse burden of proof

(short-term): Enforce regulations that require importers to provide documented proof of the origin of coffee and other products to ensure they are not associated with forced labour. Develop and utilize advanced technologies, such as blockchain and traceability systems, to provide reliable and verifiable proof of product origin.

Impact assessment of trade agreements

(short-term): Conduct comprehensive impact assessments before and after trade agreements to evaluate their effects on local markets, poverty levels, environment, and food security. Use the findings from impact assessments to inform policy decisions and negotiate trade agreements that prioritize sustainable development and poverty reduction.

Promote voluntary certification schemes for local and export markets

(short-term & middle-term): Encourage farmers and agricultural businesses to participate in voluntary certification schemes that promote environmental

objectives and ensure compliance with sustainable practices. Provide financial incentives and technical assistance to support the implementation and maintenance of certification schemes, including training and capacity-building programs.

Trade integration and diversification of trade routes (middle-term): Strengthen trade integration and diversify trade routes for agricultural products to reduce dependence on a single market or route. Invest in infrastructure development and logistics to improve connectivity and resilience in the trade of agricultural products.

Price observatories monitor price developments in global agricultural supply chains (short-term): Establish price observatories at different stages of the agricultural supply chain to monitor and analyze price changes, providing valuable information for market participants. Collaborate with relevant stakeholders to ensure the transparency and accessibility of price observatory data, enabling informed decision-making.

De-Commodification (middle-term): Develop educational programs and campaigns to raise awareness among small farmers about the importance of value addition and differentiated production. Support farmers in accessing training, technology, and resources necessary for value-added processing and marketing of their agricultural products.

Support value-addition activities (middle-term): Provide technical cooperation and capacity-building programs to support value-addition activities in third countries, enabling farmers to enhance the value and quality of their products. Explore options for tariff reductions or exemptions to incentivize value-addition activities and promote trade opportunities for processed agricultural products.

Governments put in place binding HREDD obligations (long-term): Enact legislation that mandates chocolate and other companies to conduct comprehensive analyses of their purchasing practices' impact on living income and take necessary actions to ensure fair compensation. Establish regulatory mechanisms and penalties to enforce compliance with HREDD obligations and hold companies accountable for their impact on living income.

Differentiation between and grouping of products based on quality attributes (short-term & middle-term): Develop labeling and certification schemes that differentiate products based on specific quality attributes, such as organic, fair trade, or sustainable production practices. Collaborate with industry stakeholders and consumer organizations to promote awareness and demand for products with desirable quality attributes.

Financing for certification (short-term & middle-term): Create dedicated funding mechanisms or grants to support farmers and businesses in covering the costs of obtaining and maintaining certification for sustainable and quality production. Explore partnerships with financial institutions and impact investors to provide accessible and affordable financing options specifically for certification purposes.

Sustainability dimension - Social and Human

Living income for farmers & agriculture (short-term): Establish a minimum price guarantee for agricultural products that ensures farmers receive a living income, covering the cost of living, operation, and basic needs.

Living Wages / Income (short-term & middle-term): Advocate for the implementation of fair wage policies and regulations that ensure farm workers receive living wages. Encourage companies to commit to paying living wages to farmers and farm workers through voluntary agreements or certification schemes.

Fair and sustainable value chains (middle-term): Develop and promote fair trade certification schemes that guarantee fair prices for farmers and ensure transparency in costs and prices throughout the value chain. Advocate for policies and regulations that promote equitable pricing and market power distribution within value chains.

A gender transformation approach to HREDD processes (middle-term): Integrate a gender transformative approach into companies' human rights due diligence (HREDD) processes, conducting risk assessments that consider and address gender-based vulnerabilities and discrimination. Develop gender-specific measures and interventions to promote gender equality and empowerment within value chains.

Preservation of export products for the local market (middle-term): Enact legislation that requires companies involved in exporting food products to allocate a certain percentage of their production for the local market, ensuring food security and availability for local communities. Implement incentives and support programs to encourage companies to prioritize domestic market supply when exporting food products.

Sustainability standards and legislation designed to avoid perverse effects on small-scale producers and cooperatives (short-term, middle-term & long-term): Develop and enforce sustainability standards and legislation that specifically consider the impact on small-scale producers and cooperatives, ensuring that compliance burdens are primarily placed on larger companies in the value chains. Strengthen the role and position of cooperatives as key stakeholders in value chains through policy measures and support programs that enhance their capacity and bargaining power.

Sustainability dimension - Natural Capital

Adoption of sustainable farming practices and biodiversity conservation (short-term): Develop and implement agro-ecology programs that promote sustainable farming practices, focus on social issues and local content, and support food security and incomes. Establish institutionalized frameworks and support systems for agro-ecology, providing training and resources to farmers to adopt sustainable practices and conserve biodiversity.

Producers that earn a living income are better equipped to deal with climate adaptation and increase disaster resilience (long-term): Implement measures to improve producer income, such as fair pricing mechanisms and access to markets, to enhance their capacity to adapt to climate change and increase resilience to disasters. Provide financial and technical support to help farmers invest in climate-smart agriculture practices and technologies.

Sustainable water use & management in agriculture (short-term): Promote water-efficient farming practices to reduce water waste and absolute water use, including the use of precision irrigation techniques and water-saving technologies. Encourage the implementation of water recycling and reuse systems in agricultural operations.

Biodiversity (middle-term): Implement policies and initiatives to prevent deforestation linked to agro-ecological practices, such as promoting sustainable land use and forest conservation. Strengthen global value chain governance to account for biodiversity considerations, ensuring that supply chains prioritize biodiversity conservation. Support farmers, especially small-scale farmers, in preserving agro-biodiversity through training, access to diverse seed varieties, and sustainable farming methods.

International monitoring and enforcement mechanism(s) (middle-term): Establish an international monitoring and enforcement mechanism to ensure compliance with environmental regulations, including those related to biodiversity conservation and sustainable farming practices. Collaborate with international organizations and governments to develop and implement standardized monitoring and reporting frameworks for environmental performance.

Internalization of external costs (long-term): Develop mechanisms to quantify and price the exploitation of natural capital, ensuring that the costs of environmental degradation are internalized in production and consumption processes. Promote the use of economic instruments, such as environmental taxes or cap-and-trade systems, to incentivize sustainable practices and discourage harmful activities.

Awarding system to create positive incentive for compliance (middle-term): Establish an awarding system that recognizes and rewards businesses and farmers that demonstrate responsible and sustainable practices. Provide incentives, such as tax benefits or access to preferential markets, for compliance with sustainability standards and certifications.

Learning from Good Practice Models (middle-term): Facilitate knowledge sharing and learning from successful sustainable farming models and practices through platforms, workshops, and exchange programs. Establish networks and partnerships to connect farmers, researchers, and experts to share best practices and innovative approaches.

Incentivizing support (long-term): Create incentives, such as subsidies or grants, to support awareness campaigns on regulations and the adoption of certifications. Develop financial support programs to assist farmers and businesses in obtaining certifications and licenses for sustainable practices.

Renewable energy reward system (long-term): Implement a renewable energy reward system specifically targeting the youth population, providing incentives and benefits for their active participation and contribution to renewable energy generation and consumption.

Changing consumer consumption habits (short-term): Launch consumer awareness campaigns to educate and inform the public about the environmental impacts of their dietary and consumption habits. Promote sustainable and responsible consumption practices through targeted messaging and initiatives that encourage reduced meat consumption and support deforestation-free industries.

Support knowledge-sharing and capacity building initiatives (middle-term): Establish knowledge-sharing platforms and training programs for farmers, intermediaries, and consumers to promote the adoption of best agricultural practices and enhance consumer awareness and understanding of sustainable agriculture. Allocate funding and resources to support capacity building initiatives that focus on sharing expertise and experiences among farmers and stakeholders.

Lack of incentives for farmers to expand (middle-term): Develop incentive programs, such as grants or subsidies that encourage farmers to expand their operations and adopt sustainable practices. Collaborate with financial institutions to provide access to affordable loans and financial support specifically designed to incentivize farm expansion.

Increase yield per area rather than area for farming (long-term): Invest in research and development to identify and promote innovative farming techniques and technologies that enhance productivity per unit of land area. Provide training and technical assistance to farmers to optimize their agricultural practices and achieve higher yields without expanding their farming areas.

Increase commodity productivity (long-term): Establish funding mechanisms, such as sustainability investment funds or premiums, to incentivize farmers to invest in improving commodity productivity. Create partnerships with agricultural research institutions and organizations to develop and disseminate best practices and technologies for increasing commodity productivity.

Establish sustainability investment funds (premiums) (long-term): Create dedicated sustainability investment funds that provide financial resources and support to farmers who cannot afford certifications. Design these funds to offer premium incentives for farmers to adopt and implement sustainable practices, ensuring that financial barriers do not hinder their ability to participate in certification programs. Collaborate with financial institutions, governments, and international organizations to establish and manage these funds, leveraging public-private partnerships to maximize their impact.

Guidelines for sustainable water management in agriculture (short-term): Develop and widely disseminate guidelines for sustainable water management practices in agriculture, ensuring efficient irrigation methods, water conservation, and proper treatment of wastewater. Provide training and support to farmers to implement these guidelines and adopt sustainable water management practices.

Increase / support afforestation in Africa (long-term): Launch afforestation initiatives in Africa, providing support and resources to local communities and foresters to increase tree planting and reforestation efforts. Collaborate with international organizations to secure funding and technical assistance for afforestation projects in Africa, with a focus on providing alternative fuel sources and improving livelihoods.

Insurance and re-insurance in the face of climate change induced natural disasters (short-term, middle-term & long-term): Establish insurance and re-insurance programs specifically tailored to farmers to mitigate the financial risks associated with climate change-induced natural disasters. Advocate for policies and incentives that promote the availability and accessibility of insurance products for farmers, including flexible payment options and exchange mechanisms.

Implementation of nature based solutions for water allocation to comply with environmental regulation (short-term, middle-term & long-term): Promote the adoption of nature-based solutions for water allocation in agriculture to ensure compliance with environmental regulations. Develop and implement standardized methodologies for integrating nature-based solutions into water management practices, focusing on enhancing productivity while preserving environmental integrity.

Standardized methodology for environmental impact assessment on trade (middle-term & long-term): Establish a standardized methodology for conducting environmental impact assessments of international trade activities, particularly in the agricultural sector. Collaborate with international trade organizations and governments to incorporate environmental considerations into trade agreements and policies.

International cooperation and agreements to reduce beef-industry related deforestation (short-term, middle-term & long-term): Foster international cooperation and agreements to address deforestation linked to the beef industry, including promoting sustainable land use practices and supporting alternative protein sources. Advocate for stricter regulations and enforcement mechanisms to prevent land conversion for beef production and ensure sustainable practices throughout the supply chain.

International monitoring of compliance with environmental regulations (short-term, middle-term & long-term): Establish an international monitoring and enforcement mechanism to ensure countries' compliance with environmental regulations, particularly in relation to agriculture and natural resource management. Strengthen international cooperation and information sharing to promote transparency and accountability in environmental governance.

Fair trade certification and labelling programs (short-term and middle-term): Implement and promote fair trade certification and labeling programs to establish standards for fair pricing, working conditions, and environmental sustainability in supply chains. Encourage consumers and businesses to support fair trade products through awareness campaigns and incentives, fostering a market that values and supports the livelihoods of producers.

Sustainability dimension - Policy, Governance and Regulation

Strong local Institutions and capacities for sustainable trade (short-term & middle-term): Establish capacity-building programs and initiatives that focus on knowledge exchange and skill development for farmers and intermediaries in sustainable trade. Allocate funding and resources to support the creation of local institutions that promote trust, transparency, and knowledge sharing among stakeholders in the trade value chain. Develop training programs on future markets, labeling regulations, and other relevant

topics to enhance the capacity of farmers and intermediaries to engage in sustainable trade practices.

Accountability for companies (middle-term): Enforce existing laws and regulations based on the UN guiding principles on business and human rights, ensuring that companies are held accountable for their actions and impacts. Develop and implement national action plans that outline specific measures and requirements for companies to conduct human rights due diligence (HREDD) in their operations and supply chains.

Obligatory HREDD for Companies (short-term): Introduce mandatory requirements for companies to conduct HREDD, focusing on the rights and well-being of affected stakeholders and rights holders. Enhance the transparency and disclosure of companies' HREDD processes and outcomes, enabling stakeholders to hold them accountable.

Fair global standards (short-term): Advocate for the development and adoption of fair global standards that bridge the gap between different farming practices, technologies, knowledge, skills, and profits. Promote the implementation of contract farming practices between investors and farmers to ensure fair and equitable relationships, access to markets, and better prices for farmers.

A comprehensive revision of the EUDR (short-term): Conduct a comprehensive review and revision of the European Union Deforestation-free Regulation (EUDR), specifically to include "Other Wooded Land" and "Natural Grassland" in the definition of forests. Introduce additional provisions and requirements that strengthen the regulation's effectiveness in combating deforestation and promoting sustainable land use practices.

Policy dialogues between large agricultural traders (short-term): Facilitate policy dialogues and engagement between large agricultural traders, particularly with influential traders such as China, to discuss and promote the evolution of social and environmental trade standards in their respective markets. Foster collaboration and knowledge sharing to drive positive change in global agricultural trade practices.

Re-purposing tax revenues (long-term): Explore the possibility of re-purposing tax revenues to invest in local value chains that are crucial for food

security and development. Consider taxing produce from regions that contribute to overproduction, redirecting those funds to support local value chains and promote self-sufficiency.

Sustainable Investment (middle-term): Align sustainable investment strategies with local development policies and global value chains, reducing over-dependency on external markets and resources. Differentiate between loans and grants to provide targeted financial support for sustainable investments, promoting transparency and accountability in the use of funds.

Follow-up

The outcomes from the webinars, including the categorized actions and the structured sketch of the roadmap, formed the basis for further discussions, refinement, and implementation planning in subsequent workshops and project activities.

By combining the thematic elements of the vision-parts - according to the different sustainability dimensions - with the categorized timeline, the resulting integrated roadmap will provide a strategic framework for the development of transition pathways. It highlighted the necessary measures and actions to be taken at different stages, ensuring a systematic and coherent approach towards achieving the shared vision. This roadmap will be further developed during the WP5 workshop on "Transition Pathways" in Brussels in March 2024.